

(Emblem of
UNNES)

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
UNIVERSITAS NEGERI SEMARANG
FACULTY OF MATHEMATICS AND SCIENCE

Building D12, Dean's Office of FMIPA
UNNES Sekaran Campus, Gunungpati,
Semarang City 50229
Tel. (024) 86008700 Ext. 400
<https://unnes.ac.id/mipa/>
mipa@mail.unnes.ac.id

Number : B/7758/UN37.1.4/PT.01.04/2025
Matter : Research Permit

May 5, 2025

To: Dean of FPMIPATI UPGRIS
GU 1st floor, Jl. Throw No. 1 Semarang

With respect, we hereby convey that the following students:

Name : Joko Saefan
Student ID : 2304200018
Study Program : Natural Sciences Education, Doctoral Program
Semester : Even
Academic Year : 2024/2025
Research Title : Development of Dynamic Modeling-Based Learning to Enhance Scientific Creativity in the Physics Domain

We request that the person concerned be granted permission to conduct research at the company or agency that you lead, with a time allocation of May 7, 2025 to May 15, 2025.

We thank you for your attention and cooperation.

On behalf of Dean of FMIPA
Vice Dean for Academic and Student Affairs

(signed)

Zaenal Abidin, S.Si., M.Cs., Ph.D.
NIP 198205042005011001

CC:
Dean of FMIPA

Balai Besar
Sertifikasi
Elektronik

This document has been electronically signed using an
electronic certificate issued by BSrE.

UNNES Official Letter Information System

2025-05-05 07:17:52

